

Progress in SR-ELEXIS Semantic Annotation: Focusing on Multiword Expressions, Named Entities, and Sense Repository

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1 Introduction

ELEXIS-WSD is a parallel sense-annotated corpus in which content words (nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs) have been assigned senses for 10 languages. The list of sense inventories is based depending on a language either on WordNet, Wiktionary, or some national digital dictionary (Federico et al., 2021). We started developing the sense-annotated corpus for Serbian that would be compatible with ELEXIS-WSD. This work is done in the scope of WG2.T2 (Barbu Mititelu et al., 2024) of the UniDive COST action (Savary et al., 2024); the first results of this endeavor were presented in (Krstev et al., 2024a,b). Figure 1 presents the progress in achieving our goal while the following sections give reasons why some tasks took considerable time.

Figure 1: The pipeline for the preparation of the Serbian dataset; green boxes – the finished tasks; pink boxes – work in progress, lilac boxes – pending tasks.

2 Completed tasks

The TRANSLATION from the English corpus of 2,024 sentences has been completed. Care was taken to ensure that the translation was in the spirit of the Serbian language, as well as to maintain the meaning of the sentences in English.

Tokenization, lemmatization, and POS-tagging were done automatically (Stankovic et al., 2020; Stanković et al., 2022), and controlled by at least three evaluators. There were several issues concerning TOKENIZATION which had to be resolved; we will single out just a few of them: (a) Ordinal numbers written with digits and followed by a dot (as used in dates) (Ex1) or followed by a hyphen and an inflectional ending (as used in other instances) are considered as one token (Ex4). (b) An acronym followed by a hyphen and an inflectional ending is considered as one token (Ex2). (c) Compounds written with a hyphen are treated as three tokens (Ex3). As a result, we obtained a corpus ELEXIS-SR containing 31,058 tokens and 27,378 words. The average length of sentences in tokens is 15.34.

Some of the several questions that arose during the POS-TAGGING were resolved as follows: (a) Ordinal numbers written with digits or spelled are treated as adjectives (Ex5). (b) Passive past participles are treated as verbs (Ex6) or as adjectives (Ex7), depending on a context. Since the UD annotation guidelines allow participles to be annotated as adjectives, verbs or even nouns, we decided to annotate them according to their syntactic function (as ADJ, VERB or NOUNS, respectively). (c) Non-transcribed foreign words or names were categorized as ‘other’ (Ex8), while transcribed foreign words or names were assigned the appropriate category (Ex9). The distribution of POS tags

in the corpus ELEXIS-SR is: NOUN 7,656, ADJ 3,964, PUNCT 3,680, VERB 2,920, ADV 2,818, AUX 2,195, PROPN 1,492, CCONJ 1,266, DET 1,094, ADV 1,026, SCONJ 727, PART 684, NUM 650, X 552, PROPN 262, SYM 72.

Among the questions posed by LEMMATIZATION were: (a) Lemmas of ordinal numbers written with digits are numbers written with digits (Ex10); (b) The lemma of an acronym followed by a hyphen and an inflectional ending is the acronym itself (Ex11); (c) The lemma of the abbreviation remains unchanged (Ex12); (d) Lemmas of adjectives are in the indefinite form, if it exists (Ex13); (e) lemmas of demonyms are in singular (Ex14).

For the present NAMED ENTITY (NE) annotation step (Ex17) we used model *sr_ner_tesla_j355* (Nešić et al., 2024), which is less accurate than the SrpNER tool used for the preliminary annotation (Krstev et al., 2024a), but easier to align with other annotation tasks. In total, 2,294 NEs were manually verified. The category PRODUCT, which is not covered by the automatic annotation, was manually tagged. The results of NE evaluation per types that are relevant for assigning senses are presented in Table 1.

Tag	N ^o	R	P	F ₁	comp
PERS	429	.86	.90	.89	+0.07
LOC	710	.90	.92	.91	+0.03
ORG	330	.56	.72	.65	-0.15
DEMO	301	.93	.87	.90	-0.02
ROLE	309	.86	.79	.82	-0.08
EVENT	60	.89	.55	.68	-0.12
WORK	75	.62	.56	.59	n.a.
PRODUCT	80				

Table 1: N^o – number of recognized NEs by *sr_ner_tesla_j355*; R, recall; P, precision; F₁ measure; **comp** – difference in F₁ in relation to SrpNER.

Named entities were manually linked with Wikidata using the INCEpTION platform (Klie et al., 2018). As a result, 1,949 NEs were linked with the existing Wikidata items, leaving presently 345 unconnected NEs. Figure 2 presents the linking results per NE categories.

3 Tasks in progress

The ELEXIS-SR corpus was tagged with MULTIPLE WORD EXPRESSIONS (MWE) – Ex15, including verbal expressions (VMWE) – Ex16, using same tools and resources used for preliminary tag-

Figure 2: NEs lined with Wikidata (blue); NEs not yet linked with Wikidata (orange).

Gr.	Type	N ^o _f	N ^o _l	R	P	F ₁
MWE	NOUN	413	303	.37	.95	.66
	PNOUN	136	73	.76	1.	.87
	ADV	45	21	.20	1.	.33
	ADJ	2	2		n.a.	
VMWE	IRV	205	83	1.	1.	1.
	LVC _{FULL}	43	28	.75	1.	.86
	VID	12	9		n.a.	
	LVC _{CAUSE}	10	7		n.a.	

Table 2: Annotated MWEs in ELEXIS-SR per type – N^o_f, number of forms; N^o_l, number of lemmas; R, recall; P, precision; F₁ measure.

ging (Krstev et al., 2024a). In this run, more expressions were retrieved (710 MWEs vs. 653, and 270 VMWEs vs. 228), mostly due to the enhancement of lexical resources used. We performed the evaluation of results on 5% of sentences from the ELEXIS-SR corpus and results are presented in Table 2. Note that only those MWEs that will eventually be assigned a sense are listed.

Since there is no freely available digital descriptive dictionary of the Serbian language, the Serbian SENSE REPOSITORY (WSD-SR) will be based on the Serbian WordNet – SrpWN (Stanković et al., 2018), which needs to be extended.

To detect the missing synsets, we started from the English ELEXIS sense repository, which is based on the Princeton WordNet (PWN). Out of 16,106 entries from the ELEXIS-EN sense repository, we aligned 13,703 PWN synsets by comparing their definitions. At that moment, the SrpWN contained a total of 25,322 synsets, and we matched 5,997 synsets with the ELEXIS-EN sense repository through the interlingual index. The missing subset was compared with sentence annotations in ELEXIS-EN, which revealed that the “urgent” first step was to fill the gap with 2,130 synsets.

The automatic translations of synonyms and synset definitions from the PWN using Google API and OpenAI services were postedited.

In the next step, we retrieved a list of all content words (common nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs) from 2,024 sentences. The content words that were not in SrpWN were translated to English to retrieve 1,795 candidates from PWN for the next round of automatic translation followed by postediting. In addition to that, 355 synsets were added as hypernyms of new synsets. Out of these 2,150 synsets, postediting is done for 1,526 synsets, while the control of the remaining 624 synsets is in progress (36 adjectives, 3 verbs, 584 nouns, 1 adverb), expected to be finished soon.

Table 3 presents an overview of the coverage of content words with entries in the sense repository: column *Yes* means that there is at least one synset per word, while *No* shows missing senses. The nouns and verbs are presently better covered than adjectives and adverbs. We expect that when the second round of postediting is finished producing the new 624 synsets, we will reach high coverage for nouns and verbs. For adjectives and adverbs, an additional expansion round and some new strategy will be required.

UPOS	Yes	No	Total	Yes%	No%
NOUN	2007	419	2426	82.7	17.3
VERB	749	121	870	86.1	13.9
ADJ	814	471	1285	63.3	36.7
ADV	174	82	256	68.0	32.0
total	3744	1093	4837	77.4	22.6

Table 3: Sense repository coverage for the WSD-SR.

4 Future activities

The first next tasks that await us are a detailed evaluation and correction of the MWE and VMWE annotation, as well as completion of NE linking. These will be followed by parallel activities: sense repository finalization, semi-automatic meaning assignment, and syntactic annotation.

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A Example Appendix

- Ex1 | 19. | juna | 2010. | ‘on 19th June 2010’;
- Ex2 | u | IBM-u | ‘in IBM’;
- Ex3 | remek | - | delo | ‘master-piece’;
- Ex4 | 16-bitni | ‘having 16 bites’;
- Ex5 5._{ADJ} ‘5th’, peti_{ADJ} ‘fifth’;
- Ex6 upotreba oružja je ograničena_{VERB} zakonom ‘the use of weapons is limited by law’;
- Ex7 poljoprivreda je prilično ograničena_{ADJ} ‘agriculture is quite limited.’
- Ex8 objavio je svoj Słownik_X chemiczny_X ‘he published his Słownik chemiczny’;
- Ex9 Nju_{NPROP} Jorker_{NPROP} je američki časopis ‘The New Yorker is an American magazine’;
- Ex10 5._{LEMMA=5} ‘5th’, peti_{LEMMA=peti} ‘fifth’;
- Ex11 u IBM-u_{LEMMA=IBM} ‘in IBM’;
- Ex12 i_{LEMMA=i} sl._{LEMMA=sl.} abbreviated from i slično ‘and similar’;
- Ex13 pre velikih_{LEMMA=velik} sastanaka ‘before major meetings’;
- Ex14 Rimljani_{LEMMA=Rimljanin} su podigli utvrđenje ‘The Romans built a fort there’;
- Ex15 Nauru je nakratko postao <MWE pos="NOUN" lemma="poreski raj"> poreski raj </MWE> i centar za ilegalno <MWE pos="NOUN" lemma="pranje novca">. ‘Nauru briefly became a tax haven and illegal money laundering centre.’
- Ex16 Godine 1968. <VMWE type="IRV" id="v1" lemma="udati se"> udala </VMWE> <VMWE type="IRV" id="p1"> se </VMWE> za grčkog brodskog magnata Aristotela Onazisa. ‘In 1968, she married Greek shipping magnate Aristotle Onassis.’
- Ex17 <role> Trenutni ombudsman </role> <pers> Emili O’Rajli </pers> iz <top> Irske </top> stupila je na dužnost <time> 1. oktobra 2013. godine </time>. ‘The current Ombudsman, Emily O’Reilly of Ireland, took office on 1 October 2013.’